

FACTORS THAT CHALLENGE IMPLEMENTATION OF A BUILDING ENERGY RETROFIT PROJECT

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Abstract

Building energy retrofits is one of the global strategies to achieve net zero carbon emissions. This building alteration has prompted revisions in regulatory frameworks and technical recommendations to enhance the energy efficiency of existing structures. However, building energy retrofit is an important step towards Net Zero, but it comes with significant challenges, such as a lack of clarity within existing regulations, along with the limitations of technical solutions. To this end, this paper positions itself to unravel challenges faced by professionals in South Africa. Hence, a purposive sample was expedited to elicit information from the experts. A total of 68 questionnaire surveys were electronically administered, and 38 were received back, which represents a 66% response rate, and these form the basis of this analysis. The result indicates that the challenges that top the list are lack of the required technical know-how, high investment cost, limited access to finance, lack of flexibility/adaptability in the delivery process, piecemeal-fashion energy efficiency implementation, uncertainty about the payback period, and lack of broad buy-in into the project, with mean scores of 4.47, 4.47, 4.18, 4.21, 4.13, 4.13, and 4.13, respectively. It is notable that the above-mentioned challenges have MSes of $> 4.00 < 4.50$ and can thus be deemed major challenges, which indicates in general that they hamper delivery of building energy retrofit projects to a great extent. The practical ramifications of the challenges in energy retrofitting encompass halted projects, inadequate performance results, wasted resources, and adverse effects on occupant health and climate change mitigation objectives.

Keywords: Building Challenge Energy Retrofit South Africa.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Rapidly enhancing energy retrofits for existing buildings is crucial to meet climate goals (Freya, Aaron and Palmer, 2025). Furthermore, the global construction sector accounts for around 37% of annual carbon emissions (United Nations Environment Programme, 2022). The current energy retrofit standards for buildings in industrialised nations must be substantially elevated to reduce carbon emissions and achieve critical climate goals (Bobrova, Papa Christos, and Cooper, 2022; European Academies Science Advisory Council, 2021). The built environment must be improved to mitigate the unavoidable effects of climate change and decrease operational costs (Ling and Niig, 2016).

Africa encounters considerable challenges in sustainable energy advancement, notwithstanding its rich natural resources. If done well, it may satisfy local requirements while also tackling global issues such as desertification, environmental degradation, and greenhouse gas emissions (Aliyu et al., 2018). Numerous older residences demonstrate energy inefficiency and insufficient sustainability. However, the exclusive solution cannot involve the demolition and restoration of the property, as it is just impracticable. The resolution lies in the refurbishment of existing building, which will diminish operational costs and improve the overall sustainability of the homes (Wilkinson and Sayce, 2019).

Since existing building represent the majority of the built environment, it is imperative to initiate energy retrofits to reduce consumption and costs related to heating, cooling, and lighting. The Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB) in South Africa has underscored the imperative of upgrading the country's building portfolio (Milford, 2009). However, energy conservation is not the only reason for retrofitting existing structures; such alterations can also promote the creation of high-performance buildings (Paradis, 2012; Okorafor, 2019).

Nevertheless, retrofitting as an option is still in its infancy in South Africa. Five indicators delineate this situation: the lack of a delivery system for retrofitting, the omission of energy retrofitting from the official rate schedules of governmental entities, a dearth of contractors and skilled artisan's adept in this field, limited knowledge among professionals concerning retrofitting alternatives, and inadequate information on retrofitting (Okorafor, Emuze and Das, 2019). The execution of retrofitting to mitigate carbon emissions is fraught with challenges, making it unattainable for the common person (Milford, 2009). This study sought to clarify the challenges faced by retrofit tradesmen in doing building energy retrofits in South Africa.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Energy is an essential resource as virtually all human operations are dependent on it. The importance of energy to the growth and development of any nation (developed and developing) cannot be disputed. As compared to other sectors of the economy, buildings are known to have a high percentage of energy consumption, although the rate of each country and region differs (Masoso and Grobler, 2010; Gul and Patidar, 2015). For example, the industrial sector is the largest consumer of energy at almost 62 percent while the domestic/household consumption account for 20 percent of the total energy consumption in South Africa (South African Department of Energy, 2019; Deloitte, 2017).

It is therefore difficult for the government to meet all the energy needs of the increasing population, leading to load shedding in some parts of the country and total blackout in some other parts. In Nigeria, the slow pace at which the economy grows is attributed to the issue of energy as all commercial and industrial operations is solely dependent on it. The inefficiency of the energy sector has also crippled the growth and development of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) which are known to be a significant driver of the economy in developing countries. As affirmed by (Terrapon-Pfaff, Dienst, König and Ortiz, 2014). Lack of access to energy significantly lessen the chances of eradicating poverty and constitute a crucial barrier to the growth and development of the economy. In summary, there are numerous negative issues attributed to lack of access and inadequacy of energy in any country.

It is, therefore, imperative to make efforts in enhancing efficient energy use and reduction in energy consumption. The term energy efficiency originates as a response to the various challenges encountered through energy use. Energy efficiency can be described as the ability to do more task with less energy (Sustainable Energy Africa, 2009). Many stakeholders in the energy industry believed that energy efficiency offers a positive avenue through conservation policies thereby saving cost (Allcott and Greenstone, 2012) and reducing negative

environmental impacts associated with energy use. Reduction in the per unit price of energy is considered as one of the prime gains of efficient consumption of energy (Greening, Greene and Difiglio, 2000). As supported by (Herring, 2006), energy efficiency reduces the cost of energy, making its use more affordable and a paramount avenue for reducing carbon footprint. Energy efficiency is considered as the panacea to curbing and mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and a vital factor in achieving energy policy goals (Gillingham, Newell and Palmer, 2009).

2.1 Building energy retrofit project

As stated by Okorafor et al. (2019) and Passoni et al. (2024), retrofitting buildings in the built environment entails enhancing existing structures to augment their performance, functionality, resilience, and sustainability without constructing new ones. The authors claim that it encompasses a wide range, from structural reinforcements like seismic retrofits to enhancements in energy efficiency and environmental sustainability (Okorafor et al., 2019; Passoni et al., 2024). Energy retrofit projects for buildings frequently incorporate sophisticated technology and materials to prolong building lifespan, enhance energy efficiency, and mitigate environmental effects (Okorafor, Chetty and Haupt, 2021).

A multitude of factors propels the growing emphasis on retrofitting structures within the built environment. Global concerns, including climate change and the persistent energy crisis, necessitate an immediate decrease in greenhouse gas emissions and energy consumption within the building sector, a significant contributor to global emissions (Okorafor et al., 2021; Lakhari et al., 2024). The significance of upgrading buildings has escalated as sustainability mandates align with economic and social factors. Energy retrofit solutions demonstrate considerable potential to diminish operational energy consumption and carbon emissions, thereby aiding in the attainment of global climate objectives (Kadrić, Aganović, and Kadrić, 2023; Lakhari et al., 2024). Simultaneously, retrofitting enhances tenant comfort and health by elevating indoor environmental quality, thereby aligning with overarching sustainable development objectives.

Moreover, retrofit expenditures are progressively acknowledged for their cost-efficiency over the lifespan of buildings, as they reconcile initial costs with long-term savings in energy expenses and maintenance (Kadrić, Aganović and Kadrić, 2023). This comprehensive significance underscores that retrofitting is an essential instrument for transforming the building stocks towards sustainability (Gillingham, et al, 2009). Nonetheless, energy retrofitting in buildings is marked by various challenges (Milford, 2009; Okorafor, 2019). This study intends to evaluate the challenges encountered by tradesmen in implementing building retrofitting in South Africa.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research paper employed a quantitative approach to evaluate challenges faced by tradesmen in implementing a building energy retrofit. This study utilised a purposive sampling method to gather the perspectives of the respondents. This is because few contractors in South Africa are engaged in this type of work. A list of variables identified in the literature was utilised to develop a questionnaire aimed at fulfilling the research objective.

The questionnaire was used to gather data from experts. The questionnaire consists of two sections: the first section collects demographic information from respondents, and the second section analyses the experience of tradesmen in South Africa. Researchers chose this methodology to identify individuals with knowledge of the subject under study (Creswell and Poth, 2018). The main drawback of purposive sampling is its tendency to introduce bias, as participants are selected based on predetermined criteria, resulting in a non-representative sample that limits the generalisability of the findings to the broader population (Ahmed, 2024).

This study mitigated response bias by ensuring the anonymity and confidentiality of responses, employing neutral and explicit survey questions, and utilising diverse data collection methods to validate participant feedback and reduce the influence of social desirability or other biases (Bergen and Labonte, 2019). The experts were asked to rate the severity of various issues that challenge smooth implementation of a retrofit project, using a five-point scale, with the options of 1 (minor), 2 (near-minor), 3 (neutral), 4 (near-major), and 5 (major). The five-point scale was converted to mean percentages (MPs) and mean scores (MSes) for each of the aspects as rated by the respondents. The researchers used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 16 software to analyse the obtained data.

4.0 FINDINGS

The researcher focused on respondents with practical experience in delivering building energy retrofit projects in South Africa, utilising contact information accessible online. The sampling of these groups was conducted purposefully. A total of 68 electronic questionnaire surveys were distributed, with 38 responses received, resulting in a 66% response rate. The study achieved a response rate of 66%, as shown in Table 1 below. The response rate was deemed adequate for analysis, as Moser and Kalton (1971) contend that survey results can be considered acceptable with a return rate as low as 30–40%.

Table 1: Demographics of the experts

Category	Classification	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Female	9	24%
	Male	29	76%
Years of experience	5–10 years	8	21%
	10–15 years	15	39%
	15–20 years	12	32%
	20 years or more	3	8%
Profession	Architect	4	11%
	Electrical engineer	13	34%
	Facility manager	7	18%
	Mechanical engineer	8	21%
	Project manager	4	11%
	Construction manager	2	5%

Source: Author (2025)

Table 1 indicates that among the 38 respondents, 76% identified as male and 24% as female. The table shows that 21% of respondents possessed 5–10 years of experience, 39% had 10–15 years, 32% had 15–20 years, and 8% had 20 or more years of experience. In terms of profession, 11% of respondents identified as architects, 34% as electrical engineers, 18% as facility managers, 21% as mechanical engineers, 11% as project managers, and 5% as construction managers.

4.1 Factors that challenge implementation of a building energy retrofit project

This section evaluates the factors that hinder the implementation progress of a building energy retrofit project. Experts rated the severity of various issues affecting the smooth implementation of a retrofit project on a five-point scale: 1 (minor), 2 (near-minor), 3 (neutral), 4 (near-major), and 5 (major). The five-point scale was transformed into mean percentages (MPs) and mean scores (MSes) for each aspect as evaluated by the respondents. Table 2 presents the results of these measurements along with their corresponding rankings.

Table 2: Factors that challenge implementation of a building energy retrofit project

Challenge	Scale (%)					MS	Rank
	5	4	3	2	1		
Lack of the required technical know-how	53.00	42.00	5.00	0.00	0	4.47	1
High investment cost	53.00	42.00	5.00	0.00	0	4.47	2
Limited access to finance	32.00	57.00	11.00	0.00	0	4.21	3
Lack of flexibility/adaptability in the delivery process	18.00	82.00	0.00	0.00	0	4.18	4
Piecemeal-fashion energy efficiency implementation	21.00	71.00	8.00	0.00	0	4.13	5
Lack of broad buy-in into the project	15.00	82.00	3.00	0.00	0	4.13	6
Uncertainty about the payback period	18.00	76.00	6.00	0.00	0	4.13	7
Lack of stakeholder agreement	21.00	71.00	3.00	5.00	0	4.08	8
Lack of psychosocial data in the project	16.00	76.00	5.00	3.00	0	4.05	9
Lack of as-built drawings for buildings	13.00	79.00	8.00	0.00	0	4.05	10
Poor understanding of building features	3.00	63.00	34.00	0.00	0	4.02	11
Lack of a collaborative work ethic	11.00	76.00	13.00	0.00	0	3.97	12
Lack of a standard rent or lease (income) rate for retrofitted buildings	18.00	60.00	13.00	7.00	0	3.89	13
Low stakeholder communication and consultation	16.00	60.00	18.00	6.00	0	3.87	14
Lack of existing user cooperation	11.00	55.00	29.00	5.00	0	3.71	15
Interruption of existing building operations	11.00	42.00	47.00	0.00	0	3.63	16
Delayed investment decisions	8.00	50.00	29.00	13.00	0	3.52	17
Poor selection of retrofit technologies	8.00	37.00	50.00	5.00	0	3.47	18
Education level of the occupants of the retrofitted building	8.00	32.00	57.00	3.00	0	3.45	19
Lack of user-friendly technologies	5.00	34.00	61.00	0.00	0	3.45	20

Source: (Author, 2025)

Table 2 illustrates the degree to which the 20 identified challenges impact the implementation of building energy retrofit projects within the South African construction sector, measured on a scale from 1.00 to 5.00. Notably, 55% of the challenges exhibit MSes between > 4.00 and 4.50, categorising them as major challenges. This suggests that they significantly impede the delivery of building energy retrofit projects.

Forty-five percent of the challenges exhibit MSes between 3.40 and 4.00, categorising them as near-major challenges that significantly impact the delivery of building energy retrofit projects. Table 2 indicates that the primary challenges identified include insufficient technical expertise, high investment costs, limited access to financing, inflexibility in the delivery process, fragmented energy efficiency implementation, uncertainty regarding the payback period, and inadequate stakeholder support for the project, with mean scores of 4.47, 4.47, 4.18, 4.21, 4.13, 4.13, and 4.13, respectively.

5.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings align with those reported by the Chartered Institute of Building (CIOB) in its Carbon Action 2050 initiative (2015). The findings align with several studies (see CORE net Global, 2012: iv; Miller and Buys, 2008: 345; Miller, Pogue, Gough and Davis, 2009: 15; Phoenix Electric Corporation, 2015), which indicate that energy retrofitting of existing buildings is costly and inconvenient. It adversely affects heritage and archaeological assets due to the use of unproven methods, technologies or instruments. Additionally, there is limited research on insulation mechanisms in walls and the impact of retrofitting on building. The observed challenges indicate that a lack of competition is contributing to rising costs and prices of retrofit services. This results in delays for deliveries and extended lead times, especially when services and products are limited.

A limited selection of installers and funds may hinder the procurement of energy-efficient retrofit projects. The findings indicate that the absence of stakeholder agreement, insufficient psychosocial data in the project, unavailability of as-built drawings for buildings, inadequate understanding of building features, and the lack of a standardised rent or lease rate for retrofitted buildings, with means of 4.08, 4.05, 4.05, 4.02, 3.89, and 3.87 respectively, constitute significant challenges that impede the execution of building energy retrofit projects. The challenges can be attributed to the quality of available information. The presence of original drawings significantly enhances comprehension of the design intent.

Nonetheless, drawings are not consistently accessible, necessitating the acquisition of information through on-site testing, thereby complicating delivery. The findings align with those reported in the CIOB study (2015). All challenges identified in the study exhibit above-average mean scores, indicating their equal significance. The study indicates that the aforementioned challenges may impede the execution of building energy retrofit projects. The ability to mobilise essential stakeholders for the coherent and coordinated management of complex, long-term innovations across various challenges is essential.

6.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the study, building energy retrofitting is primarily hindered by significant financial, regulatory, informational, and behavioural barriers. Overcoming these challenges requires an integrated approach involving government incentives, increased stakeholder education, and a shift in focus from short-term investment costs to long-term lifecycle benefits. The main factors hindering building energy retrofits, according to the study, can be categorised as follows: insufficient technical expertise, high investment costs, limited access to financing, inflexibility in the delivery process, fragmented energy efficiency implementation, uncertainty regarding the payback period, and inadequate stakeholder support for the project.

To accelerate the adoption of building energy retrofits, a multi-faceted approach is recommended, for example, financial incentives and diverse funding: governments should provide robust financial support, including tax incentives, subsidies, grants, and low-interest loan programmes, to reduce the impact of high upfront costs. Stronger and Clearer Regulations: Implement clear, mandatory energy efficiency standards for existing buildings and streamline the planning permission process to provide certainty and consistency across local authorities.

Enhanced Education and Information Dissemination: Launch educational campaigns to raise awareness among owners and occupants about the long-term benefits (economic, social, environmental) of retrofits. Facilitate training and capacity building for professionals and contractors to ensure a skilled workforce. Integrated Project Approaches: Encourage approaches that consider the whole lifecycle cost (LCC) and non-energy benefits (e.g., improved comfort, increased property value) rather than just initial investment costs.

Collaboration and Standardised Tools: Foster greater collaboration among all stakeholders (owners, tenants, designers, contractors, and government) and develop standardised, transparent evaluation frameworks and decision-support tools to build confidence and manage risks.

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